

Analysis of Fire Resistance in Cellular Steel Beams with Sinusoidal Openings

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Abstract

Fire safety is a major consideration in building design to protect lives and keep construction costs as low as possible. Understanding the behavior of structural fires is crucial for structural analysts during the building design process. This paper presented the numerical approach implemented within ABAQUS package to model some of the tests on Angelina steel beams at ambient temperature. There was generally a good agreement between the numerical models and the test results in terms of the failure load and the failure mode. Within the numerical validations, it was found that the failure mode (and failure load) of cellular beams with sinusoidal openings can be very sensitive to the size of the opening section. It was found that for a large opening size ($a_o/H_t=0.67$), a total yielding of the four opening corners was observed. Then, for a small opening size ($a_o/H_t=0.42$), the failure observed numerically was considered as the local buckling of two parts of the opening. Therefore, the numerical model should consider precisely the resistance of each opening quarter in the critical opening and their combination to obtain the failure mechanism of the opening. Finally, study revealed that the Angelina steel beams with tangent fillet corners are more prone to web-post buckling failure due to their reduced area of web-post section, whereas this mechanism does not occur in the case of sinusoidal openings with non-tangent fillet corners due to their wider web-post area. Observations revealed that Angelina steel beams with smaller opening-spacing-to-height ratios undergo significant deformation, resulting in web-post buckling failure at ambient temperature.

Keywords: Fire resistance; Cellular beam; Restraint; Sinusoidal openings; Thermal behavior; Mechanical response.

1. Introduction

The investigation into the fire resistance of cellular steel beams with sinusoidal openings is a critical area of research within structural engineering. Cellular steel beams, characterized by their perforated web design, offer advantages such as reduced weight and improved service integration^[1]. The sinusoidal pattern of openings further enhances these benefits by optimizing structural efficiency and aesthetic appeal. However, these modifications also introduce complexities in fire performance, necessitating a detailed

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examination^[2]. Fire resistance is a paramount concern in construction, directly influencing the safety and integrity of structures under fire exposure. The behavior of cellular steel beams during fire events is affected by the presence of openings, which can alter thermal distribution and structural stability^[3]. Understanding these effects requires comprehensive experimental and numerical analysis. Previous studies have highlighted the potential of cellular beams in various applications, yet their fire performance, particularly with sinusoidal openings, remains underexplored^[4].

This research aims to fill this gap by systematically investigating the thermal and structural responses of cellular steel beams with sinusoidal openings under fire conditions. By employing advanced simulation techniques and rigorous experimental testing, this study seeks to develop robust predictive models and design guidelines to enhance the fire safety of steel structures. The findings are expected to contribute significantly to the field of fire engineering, providing valuable insights for engineers and designers in optimizing both performance and safety of cellular steel beams in building constructions. The experimental results are used to validate the finite element model developed using the software ABAQUS. The finite element model created with ABAQUS software is validated by the experimental data^[5]. The primary experimental and numerical results were compared and reported in this thesis. When modeling a cellular beam with sinusoidal apertures at room temperature, imperfections must be taken into account. Section 4.2 illustrates how imperfections are determined and incorporated into the models.

2. Applying imperfections

Imperfections are typically incorporated into the model as perturbations from the initial geometry^[6]. These imperfections play a critical role in influencing the "buckling stability" of steel beams and should be considered when assessing their inelastic rigidity. They involve multiple superimposed buckling modes applied to the model, unless the exact shape of the imperfection is known. The consideration of imperfections in cellular beams is vital for several reasons^[7]. In practice, the cutting and fabrication process of cellular beams often results in geometric perturbations. Therefore, modeling them as intact sections is far from realistic. In this thesis, imperfections are introduced by employing a linear superposition of both local and global buckling modes into the model. This method establishes the contribution of each mode through imperfection amplitudes, as defined by equation 4-1.

$$\Delta x_i = \sum_{i=1}^M w_i \varphi_i \quad (2-1)$$

where: φ_i — is the i^{th} mode shape

w_i — is the associated scale factor

Furthermore, both initial global and local imperfections must be combined and implemented in the FEM analysis for more accurate results. When numerically modeling perforated steel sections, there is no set formula for the shape of the web-post imperfection or amplitude of the flaw^[8]. In their proposed methods, Schafer and Pekoz have suggested that the total length of the section for global buckling and the thickness of the steel plate for local buckling control the amplitude of the flaws. To find the initial local and global buckling modes (those with the lowest eigenvalues) in this procedure, the beam was subjected to a buckling

analysis [9]. In the second analysis, scale factors for the structure's buckling modes are introduced to apply imperfection to the ideal geometry. In this thesis, simulations are conducted using this approach.

3. Modelling of Angelina beams at ambient temperature

The numerical models for Angelina steel beams were validated against experiments conducted on two specimens as follows:

- 1) AS012
- 2) AS018

The tests concern two full scale of cellular beam with sinusoidal openings loaded in four-point bending as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Loading configuration of tested beams

Angelina steel beam configurations are covered by these beams with two distinct opening heights, which stand for small and medium openings, respectively. IPE 400 profile is used to create the beam with small openings, and IPE 450 profile is used to create the medium beam. Figure 2 and Table 1 describe the elementary opening's geometric parameters for the two tested beams.

Figure 2 : Geometric parameters of cellular beam with sinusoidal openings

where: S stands for opening spacing, a_0 is the opening height, w is the web-post length, l_s is the sinusoidal length, L_0 is the opening length, r is the fillet radius, t_f is the flange thickness, t_w is the web thickness, b_f is the flange width, E_a is the width of solid web at beam end and, H_t is the overall beam height.

Table 1 Geometric configurations of tested beams

Specimen	Parent profile	L mm	b_f mm	t_f mm	t_w mm	r mm	H_t mm	a_0 mm	l_s mm	L_0 mm	w mm	S mm	f_y MPa
AS012	IPE 450	10,778	190	14.6	9.4	21	675	450	638	1481	205	1681	460
AS018	IPE 400	6978	180	13.5	8.6	21	507.5	215	325	852	202	1054	460

In this study, the nonlinear analysis of the Angelina steel beam is based on the following assumptions:

- Use shell components that can accommodate significant strains, deformations, and plasticity, as well as linear and quadratic deformation methods.
- The non-linearity of both materials and geometry.
- Use the Riks (Arc-length) approach or the Newton-Raphson method to solve the problem effectively in order to investigate the local buckling behaviour.
- The numerical model takes into account the nominal properties, with the exception of the initial imperfections, where measured values are used.
- To obtain the load–displacement curve of the specimens, including the descending branch that represents the post-critical range, a non-linear analysis with elastic–plastic behavior and massive displacements is carried out with displacement control.
- The actual conditions of the experiments are represented by the boundary conditions. As shown in Figure 4.3, lateral supports and vertical supports are thus taken into consideration at the same points on the bottom flange of the beam.

Based on the experimental findings, the global load-displacement curves, failure modes, and ultimate loads of the tested beams are taken into account while validating the model. Examining the behavior of the opening in each tested beam will be a fascinating tool after the model has been validated. The following is an overview of the findings from the numerical study.

Figure 3: Positions of lateral support

3.1 Beam AS012

Beam AS012 corresponds to a medium size of opening ($a_o/Ht=0.67$). The finite membrane-strain, fully integrated, quadrilateral shell element S4R was used for the modelling of cellular beam with sinusoidal openings within ABAQUS^[10].

Figure 4: Boundary conditions and load applications of AS012 beam

Figure 4 demonstrates the beam's ABAQUS model. The beam's boundary conditions were in line with the experiment's requirements. The test indicated that lateral supports were given to the middle and both ends of the beam's top and bottom flanges, and the simulation took this into account as well.

The numerical results indicate that local buckling is the primary cause of failure mode^[11]. The iso-values of the out-of-plane displacements characterize this local instability, which is present on both the upper and lower quarters of the critical opening (see Figure 5). As shown in Figure 5, the iso-values are color-coded (red), making the maximum horizontal displacements appear in blue.

Figure 5 : Iso-values of lateral displacement

A different behavior is observed with the presence of a local buckling or plastic yielding due to Vierendeel mechanism in the sinusoidal part of the two quarters of the opening^[12]. In fact, for cellular beams with sinusoidal openings, the web-post length is large enough to avoid the web-post buckling^[13]. Therefore, as expected for test AS012, the ultimate failure mode concerns the Vierendeel mechanism.

Figure 6: Vierendeel mechanism of beam AS012 using ABAQUS

Figure 6 shows the S-shape failure mode of beam AS012 and Figure 7 shows the load-deflection curves comparison between the test results and ABAQUS software predictions. The comparison between the load–displacement curves from the numerical model and the tests shows the good accuracy of the numerical model^[14]. The vertical displacement is measured at the mid-span of the whole beam.

Figure 7: Load-vertical displacement curves for beam AS012

3.2 Beam AS018

Beam AS018 is characterized by a small size of the opening ($a_0/H_t=0.42$) and as a consequence the panels around the opening are characterized by high dimensions. AS018 beam was tested at Blaise Pascal University Clermont-Ferrand, with the aim of seeking a better insight into the behaviour of cellular beam with sinusoidal openings at ambient temperature. The beam geometries were designed to fail in various modes including local buckling, which was observed in Beam AS012.

Figure 8: Geometric dimensions of AS018 beam

Figure 8 and Table 1 shows the overall specifications of this beam. More details can be found in the test report. Experimental observations show that the failure of the cellular beams AS012 and AS018 cannot be considered as the consequence of local buckling around the opening of the sinusoidal part of the most compressed quarter as it has been noticed a reserve of strength in both cases. The failure mode observed in tests is similar to that of beam AS012 with a local failure in the sinusoidal parts of the opening. The failure of the beam can be directly linked to the local failures around the opening as shown in the numerical study, which clearly identify that the causes of the global failure of the beam can be the yielding of other parts in the critical opening.

Figure 9 :Local buckling of beam AS018 using ABAQUS

Figure 9 shows the S-shape local buckling of beam AS018 and Figure 10 shows the load-deflection curves comparison between the test results and ABAQUS software predictions. The numerical model of beam AS018 represents well the real behavior observed during the test including the evolution of the applied load versus the mid-span deflection (see Figure 10). In fact, the critical opening of beam AS018 does not reach its total yielding before the development of the local instability (lateral displacement).

Figure 10 :Load-vertical displacement curves for beam AS018

The cellular beam with sinusoidal openings can be divided into two types: sinusoidal openings with tangent fillet corners type and sinusoidal openings with non-tangent fillet corners type, as shown in Figure 11(a) and (b). The fillet corners with tangent type has a circular corner radius proportional to the opening height a_0 ($r = a_0/4$); while the fillet corners with non-tangent type has a smaller circular corner radius a_0 ($r < a_0/4$).

(a) Angelina beam with tangent fillet corners

(b) Angelina beam with non-tangent fillet corners

Figure 11 : Types of cellular beam with sinusoidal openings

- Where:
- S — is the opening spacing;
 - a_o — is the opening height;
 - w — is the web-post length;
 - r — is the filler radius;
 - L_o — is the opening length; and
 - l_s — is the sinusoidal length.

The dimensional relationships of the two types of Angelina steel beams produced by the offset openings method are as follows:

- 1) Angelina steel beam with tangent fillet corner

$$S = a_o + w \tag{3-1}$$

$$a_o = 4r \tag{3-2}$$

$$H_o = H - 2r \tag{3-3}$$

$$L_o = L - \frac{S}{2} \tag{3-4}$$

- 2) Angelina steel beam with non-tangent fillet corner

$$S = L_o + w \tag{3-5}$$

$$a_o = 4r + 2l_s \tag{3-6}$$

$$H_o = H - 2r - l_s \tag{3-7}$$

$$L_o = l_s + w \tag{3-8}$$

The sinusoidal openings with non-tangent fillet corners are characterized by a wide web-post. Thus, the web-post buckling which is a typical failure mode of cellular beams with circular openings and tangent fillet corners (see Figure 12) does not arise for sinusoidal openings with the non-tangent fillet corner.

Figure 12 :Web-post buckling of Angelina beam with tangent fillet corners

However, the sinusoidal part generates a specific mechanical behavior with local instabilities in addition to the common failure mode due to the formation of four plastic hinges around the openings. Thus, depending on the opening dimensions, the Vierendeel bending induced by the shear transfer around the opening implies either the formation of four plastic hinges in the linear part (see Figure 13) or the development of local instabilities in the critical sections of the sinusoidal part.

(a) Formation of 4 plastic hinges (beam AS012)

(b) Critical tee sections around the opening

Figure 13 : Vierendeel mechanism of Angelina beam with non-tangent fillet corners

Tables 2 and 3 provide the vertical and horizontal displacement values for Beam (AS012) and Beam (AS018) respectively and the nodes points were selected in the mid-span beams as described in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Mid-span nodes for deflection (U2, U3)

Table 2: Displacements obtained for beam AS012 in ABAQUS

Load	U2					U3
	Point A	Point B	Point C	Point D	Point E	Point F
kN	mm	mm	mm	mm	mm	mm
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2.1	-0.5	-0.5	-0.5	-0.5	-0.5	-0.008
4.2	-1.1	-1.1	-1.1	-1.1	-1.1	-0.01
7.4	-1.9	-1.8	-1.8	-1.8	-1.8	-0.03
12.3	-3.14	-3.1	-3.06	-3.1	-2.9	-0.05
19.5	-4.9	-4.9	-4.8	-4.8	-4.7	-0.08
30.4	-7.7	-7.6	-7.5	-7.4	-7.3	-0.1
46.7	-11.9	-11.7	-11.6	-11.4	-11.3	-0.1
71.1	-18.2	-17.9	-17.6	-17.4	-17.2	-0.3
105.3	-27.6	-27.2	-26.7	-26.4	-26.1	-0.5
118.1	-31.1	-30.6	-30.2	-29.7	-29.3	-0.5
123.5	-32.4	-32.1	-31.5	-31.1	-30.5	-0.6
131.2	-33.9	-33.4	-32.9	-32.4	-31.9	-0.8
133.2	-34.2	-33.7	-33.2	-32.7	-32.2	-0.8
136.1	-34.7	-34.2	-33.7	-33.2	-32.7	-0.9
140.2	-35.4	-34.9	-34.4	-34.1	-33.5	-0.9

Continued Table

146.1	-36.5	-36.07	-35.5	-35.1	-34.6	-1.04
153.6	-38.1	-37.6	-37.2	-36.7	-36.2	-1.1
150.1	-40.4	-39.9	-39.4	-38.9	-38.4	-1.15
144.1	-41.1	-40.5	-40.1	-39.4	-39.1	-1.11
140.6	-41.5	-41.1	-40.5	-40.1	-39.5	-1.09
136.6	-42.4	-41.8	-41.3	-40.8	-40.3	-1.06
132.4	-43.6	-43.1	-42.6	-42.1	-41.6	-1.04
128.1	-45.5	-45.1	-44.5	-44.1	-43.4	-1.03
123.6	-48.4	-47.9	-47.4	-46.8	-46.3	-1.01
122.2	-49.5	-49.1	-48.5	-47.9	-47.4	-1.01
120.2	-51.2	-50.6	-50.1	-49.5	-49.03	-1.007
117.8	-53.4	-52.9	-52.3	-51.8	-51.2	-1.002

Table 3 Displacements obtained for beam AS018 in ABAQUS

Load	U2					U3
	Point A	Point B	Point C	Point D	Point E	Point F
kN	mm	mm	mm	mm	mm	mm
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
7.7	-1.6	-1.6	-1.6	-1.6	-1.5	-0.002
15.5	-3.3	-3.2	-3.2	-3.2	-3.1	-0.005
27.2	-5.8	-5.7	-5.6	-5.6	-5.5	-0.009
45.01	-9.5	-9.4	-9.3	-9.2	-9.1	-0.015
72.02	-15.1	-14.9	-14.8	-14.6	-14.4	-0.024
108.1	-23.4	-23.2	-22.9	-22.6	-22.4	-0.028

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120.2	-26.5	-26.2	-25.9	-25.6	-25.4	-0.022
131.9	-31.1	-30.7	-30.4	-30.1	-29.7	0.005
144.4	-37.8	-37.4	-37.1	-36.6	-36.2	0.035
148.2	-40.3	-39.9	-39.5	-39.1	-38.6	0.043
153.5	-44.1	-43.6	-43.1	-42.7	-42.2	0.053
159.4	-49.6	-49.1	-48.6	-48.1	-47.6	0.078
163.8	-58.3	-57.8	-57.2	-56.7	-56.2	0.131
166.7	-69.6	-69.1	-68.4	-67.8	-67.3	0.191
167.9	-75.9	-75.3	-74.7	-74.1	-73.5	0.23
168.7	-80.2	-79.6	-79.1	-78.4	-77.8	0.253
169.8	-86.4	-85.7	-85.1	-84.5	-83.8	0.292
170.9	-121.7	-120.8	-120.1	-119.1	-118.3	1.081
171.6	-128.6	-127.8	-126.9	-126.1	-125.1	1.237
172.7	-139.1	-138.2	-137.2	-136.3	-135.3	1.459
173.6	-148.9	-147.9	-146.9	-145.9	-145	1.668
174.4	-157.7	-156.7	-155.6	-154.6	-153.6	1.865
175.2	-166.7	-165.7	-164.6	-163.5	-162.5	2.070

The numerical study showed that for the beams with large openings (beam AS012), the failure appears by the formation of 4 plastic hinges at the critical section of the openings quarters^[15]. Thus, the behavior is almost similar to that of steel beam with rectangular openings. Furthermore, in the case of small openings (AS018), the global failure of the beam is linked to the local buckling of two quarters combined with two plastic hinges in the post-critical stage^[16]. This failure can be assimilated to a mechanism with three or four critical sections.

Figure 15(a) shows the analysis of the first mode of instability of the cellular beam with sinusoidal openings modelled on ABAQUS. The modelled beam corresponds to the AS012 beam configuration^[17]. Thus, the observed failure mode of the beam with medium opening depth ($a_o/Ht=0.67$), is due to local bending of the upper and lower quarters developing four plastic hinges which can be assimilated to Vierendeel mechanism.

(a) First mode of instability of AS012 beam

(b) First mode of instability of AS018 beam

Figure 15 Primary instability mode for Angelina beams

Figure 15(b) shows the analysis of the first mode of instability of the cellular beam with sinusoidal openings (AS018) modelled on ABAQUS. In the beam with small opening heights ($a_o/Ht=0.42$), the Vierendeel mechanism is combined with local buckling of the compressed out-stand web panel in the sinusoidal part

of the two quarters around the openings. This local buckling of the web panel, which is specific to the sinusoidal openings, influences the ultimate strength of the beam ^[18].

4 Web-post buckling of Angelina beams at ambient temperature

Cellular beams incorporating sinusoidal openings with tangent fillet corners are particularly susceptible to web-post buckling failure^[19]. This vulnerability arises from their smaller area of the web-post length and their angle of fillet radius. Analysis steps of the web-post buckling of cellular beams at ambient temperature consists of using the non-linear buckling analysis method (Riks method) to determine the load-displacement curve, where the peak of this curve represents the ultimate load capacity of the cellular beams^[20].

4.1 Novel Angelina beam with tangent fillet corners at ambient temperature

The analysis of cellular steel beam cross-section in this section uses UB457×152×52 (flange width 152.4mm, flange thickness 10.9mm, section height 449.8mm, web thickness 5mm). Thickness of the vertical stiffeners 10mm, are placed at both ends and at the mid-span to prevent overall bending-torsion buckling and local buckling failure. Figure 4.16 describe the modelled beam on ABAQUS.

Figure 16: Boundary conditions of Angelina steel beam with tangent fillet corners

The parameter dimensions are described in Table 4. Each example is carried out according to the steps of static analysis to analyze the web-post buckling of cellular beam with sinusoidal openings.

Table 4: Geometric dimensions of Angelina steel beams

Specimen	Ht mm	L mm	S mm	a ₀ mm	w mm	S/a ₀ kN	r mm	t _w mm
BEAM-1	449.8	1890	480	315	165	1.5	78.75	5
BEAM-2	449.8	1890	450	315	135	1.4	78.75	5
BEAM-3	449.8	1890	430	315	115	1.3	78.75	5
BEAM-4	449.8	1890	400	315	85	1.2	78.75	5

The opening spacing-to-height ratio (S/a₀) was arbitrarily adjusted to investigate the web-post buckling failure mechanism of Angelina steel beams at ambient temperatures^[21].

The selected opening-spacing-to height ratio are as follows S/a₀ :1.5, 1.4, 1.3, and 1.2. The failure modes of Angelina steel beams with different opening-spacing-to-height ratio (S/a₀) at ambient temperatures are illustrated in Figure 17.

Figure 17: Web-post buckling of Angelina steel beams at ambient temperatures

As shown in Figure 17, all the four specimens of Angelina beams fails by web-post buckling mechanism, it can be seen that web-post buckling occurs with large deformation in beams featuring smaller opening-spacing-to-height ratios (S/a_o), attributed to the diminished area of the web-post section.

Figure 18 illustrates the load-displacement curves for the web-post buckling of Angelina steel beams at ambient temperatures, respectively for the 4 specimens described in the Table 4.

Figure 18 : Load-displacement curves of Angelina beams at ambient temperatures

Conclusion

Using the finite element software ABAQUS, a comprehensive analysis was conducted on the mechanical performance of a cellular beam with sinusoidal openings when subjected to fire conditions^[22]. The obtained analysis results were then used for parametric study and theoretical analysis, leading to the following conclusions: The numerical models developed for cellular beams with sinusoidal openings generally had a very good conformity with the results of the tests conducted at ambient temperature. This agreement between the numerical and test results was also good in terms of the load-displacement relationship and failure mode. This calibration of the numerical models allowed these models to be used for case studies on Angelina steel beams at both ambient and elevated temperatures. Study revealed that the Angelina steel beams with tangent fillet corners are more prone to web-post buckling deformation under ambient temperature, whereas this mechanism does not occur in the case of sinusoidal openings with non-tangent fillet corners.

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